

ARTICLE

Difference Double Sequence Space $2m(M, \phi, \Delta_m^n, p)^F$ of Fuzzy Real Numbers Defined by Double Orlicz Function

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Abstract

In this paper, we introduced the difference double sequence space $2m(M, \phi, \Delta_m^n, p)^F$ of fuzzy real numbers defined by a double Orlicz function of both $1 \leq p < \infty$ and $0 < p < 1$. We studied some properties in that sequence space as symmetricity, solidness, and convergence-free. We have proven many inclusion results too.

Key words: Orlicz Function; Completeness; Solid Space; Symmetric; Convergence-Free

Introduction

The concept of fuzzy set theory was introduced by Zadeh [[19]]. The initial works on double sequences are found in Bromwich [[14]]. Later on, it was studied by Moricz [[6]], Basarir and Sonalncan[[1]] and many others. Tripathy and Dutta [[17],[18]], Tripathy and Sarma [[15],[16]] are a few named those studied different aspect of double sequences of fuzzy real numbers.

The notion of difference sequence spaces $\varphi_\infty(\Delta)$, $c(\Delta)$ and $c_0(\Delta)$ of complex numbers was introduced by Kizmaz [[4]]. On this idea, a specific type of difference sequence spaces was introduced also studied their properties by Tripathy [[10]], Tripathy and Esi [[12]] as well as many others. A new type of difference sequence space introduced by Tripathy and Esi [13]. Later, that notion is generalized by Tripathy et al. [[7]].

Battor and Neamah [[3]] defined a double sequence as follows: a double sequence $(X, Y) = (X_{rs}, Y_{rs})$ is a double infinite array of elements (X_{rs}, Y_{rs}) , where $X = X_{rs}$ is a double infinite array of elements X_{rs} and $Y = Y_{rs}$ is infinite a double array of elements Y_{rs} , which means (X_{rs}, Y_{rs}) is complex double sequences and they defined a double Orlicz function on double sequence space in the following:

$M : [0, \infty) \times [0, \infty) \rightarrow [0, \infty) \times [0, \infty)$ such that $M(X, Y) = (M_1(X), M_2(Y))$ and $(X, Y) = (X_{rs}, Y_{rs})$ where $M_1 : [0, \infty) \rightarrow [0, \infty)$, $M_2 : [0, \infty) \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ and M_1, M_2 be two Orlicz functions which are continuous, non-decreasing, even, convex and satisfy the following conditions:

- $M_1(0) = 0, M_2(0) = 0 \Rightarrow M(0, 0) = (M_1(0), M_2(0)) = (0, 0)$
- $M_1(X) > 0, M_2(Y) > 0 \Rightarrow M(X, Y) = (M_1(X), M_2(Y)) > (0, 0)$, for all $X, Y > 0$.

- $M_1(X) \rightarrow \infty, M_2(Y) \rightarrow \infty, \text{as } X, Y \rightarrow \infty$
 $\Rightarrow M(X, Y) \rightarrow (\infty, \infty), \text{as } (X, Y) \rightarrow (\infty, \infty)$

Remark 1[[3]]

If M is a double Orlicz function, then $M_1(\lambda X) \leq \lambda M_1(X), M_2(\lambda Y)$, for all $X \geq 0, Y \geq 0$ with $0 < \lambda < 1$, so $M(\lambda X, \lambda Y) = (M_1(\lambda X), M_2(\lambda Y)) \leq \lambda(M_1(X), M_2(Y)) = \lambda M(X, Y)$, for all $(X, Y) \geq (0, 0)$, thus $M(\lambda X, \lambda Y) \leq \lambda M(X, Y)$, for all $(X, Y) \geq (0, 0)$.

Sarma [[2]] consider the classes of sequences spaces $2\omega, 2\varphi_\infty, 2c, 2c_0$ which denote the sets of all, bounded convergent and null double sequences of real or complex numbers, respectively. After that, Battor and Neamah [19] introduced $\omega^2, \varphi_\infty^2, c^2, c_0^2$ which denote the spaces of all, bounded, convergent and null of c^2 double sequences on a double Orlicz function.

Tripathy et al. [[7]] generalized difference sequence spaces; we use that idea to generalize the notion of difference double sequence spaces on a double Orlicz function as follows,

form $n \geq 1, n \geq 1$

$$Z(\Delta_m^n) = (X, Y) = (X_{rs}, Y_{rs}) : (\Delta_m^n X_{rs}, \Delta_m^n Y_{rs}) \in Z, \text{For } Z = \varphi_\infty^2, c_2^2, c_0^2$$

Where

$$\Delta_m^n X_{rs} = \Delta_m^{n-1} X_{rs} - \Delta_m^{n-1} X_{r+1,s} - \Delta_m^{n-1} X_{r,s+1} + \Delta_m^{n-1} X_{r+1,s+1}, \text{ for all } r, s \in \mathbb{N},$$

$$\Delta_m^n Y_{rs} = \Delta_m^{n-1} Y_{rs} - \Delta_m^{n-1} Y_{r+1,s} - \Delta_m^{n-1} Y_{r,s+1} + \Delta_m^{n-1} Y_{r+1,s+1}, \text{ for all } r, s \in \mathbb{N},$$

And consequently,

$$(\Delta_m^n X_{rs}, \Delta_m^n Y_{rs}) = (\Delta_m^{n-1} X_{rs} - \Delta_m^{n-1} X_{r+1,s} - \Delta_m^{n-1} X_{r,s+1} + \Delta_m^{n-1} X_{r+1,s+1}, \Delta_m^{n-1} Y_{rs} - \Delta_m^{n-1} Y_{r+1,s} - \Delta_m^{n-1} Y_{r,s+1} + \Delta_m^{n-1} Y_{r+1,s+1}), \text{ for}$$

all $r, s \in \mathbb{N}$

This generalized difference has the following binomial representation:

$$\Delta_m^n X_{rs} = \sum_{k_1=0}^n \sum_{k_2=0}^n (-1)^{k_1+k_2} \binom{n}{k_1} \binom{n}{k_2} X_{r+k_1, s+k_2} - X_{r+m, s} - X_{r, s+m}$$

And

$$\Delta_m^n Y_{rs} = \sum_{k_1=0}^n \sum_{k_2=0}^n (-1)^{k_1+k_2} \binom{n}{k_1} \binom{n}{k_2} Y_{r+k_1, s+k_2} - Y_{r+m, s} - Y_{r, s+m}$$

Then we have,

$$(\Delta_m^n X_{rs}, \Delta_m^n Y_{rs}) = (\sum_{k_1=0}^n \sum_{k_2=0}^n (-1)^{k_1+k_2} \binom{n}{k_1} \binom{n}{k_2} X_{r+k_1, s+k_2} - X_{r+m, s} - X_{r, s+m}, \sum_{k_1=0}^n \sum_{k_2=0}^n (-1)^{k_1+k_2} \binom{n}{k_1} \binom{n}{k_2} Y_{r+k_1, s+k_2} - Y_{r+m, s} - Y_{r, s+m}) \dots (1)$$

The crisp set sequence space $m(\phi)$ was introduced by Sargent [[9]], he studied some properties of this space. After that, Rath and Tripathy [[8]], Tripathy and Sen [[13]] were considered the sequence space point of view and some array classes which distinguish with one member as $m(\phi)$ in the paper, we introduced the space $2m(M, \phi, \Delta_m^n, p)^F$ of double sequences of fuzzy real numbers defined by double Orlicz function.

Throughout this paper $(\omega^2)_F, (\varphi^2)_F, (\varphi_\infty^2)_F$ denotes the spaces of all, absolutely summable, And bounded double sequences of fuzzy real numbers for a double Orlicz function, respectively.

Preliminaries and Definitions

A fuzzy number X on \mathbb{R} is a function $X: \mathbb{R} \rightarrow I=[0,1]$ associating each $t \in \mathbb{R}$, with its grade of membership $X(t)$. The class of all fuzzy real numbers is denoted by $R(I)$. For $0 < \alpha \leq 1$ the α -level set $X^\alpha = \{t \in \mathbb{R} : X(t) \geq \alpha\}$, and the 0-level set $X^0 = \{t \in \mathbb{R} : X(t) > 0\}$ is the closure of strong 0-cut, then it is compact.

The additive and multiplicative identities of $R(I)$ are denoted by $\bar{0}$ and $\bar{1}$ respectively, and the zero sequence of fuzzy real numbers is denoted by $\bar{0} = \{\bar{0}, \bar{0}, \dots\}$.

Let D denote the set of all closed bounded intervals $X=[v_1, v_2]$. We define $d : D \times D \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ by $d(X, Y) = \max\{|v_1 - w_1|, |v_2 - w_2|\}$ where $Y=[w_1, w_2]$. Clearly (D, d) is a complete metric space. Define a map $\bar{d} : R^2(I) \times R^2(I) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ by $\bar{d}(X, Y), (F, H) = \sup_{0 < \alpha \leq 1} d(X^\alpha, Y^\alpha), (F^\alpha, H^\alpha)$ for $(X, Y), (F, H) \in R^2(I)$. It is clearly that $(R^2(I), \bar{d})$ is a complete metric space. The additive and multiplicative identities of $R^2(I)$ are denoted by $(\bar{0}, \bar{0})$ and $(\bar{1}, \bar{1})$, respectively and the zero double sequence of fuzzy real numbers is denoted by $\bar{20} = \{(\bar{0}, \bar{0}), (\bar{0}, \bar{0}), \dots\}$.

A double sequence $(X, Y) = (X_{rs}, Y_{rs})$ of fuzzy real numbers on a double Orlicz is a double infinite array of elements (X_{rs}, Y_{rs}) for all $\gamma, s \in \mathbb{N}$, where $X = X_{rs}$ is a double infinite array of elements X_{rs} and $Y = Y_{rs}$ is infinite a double array of elements Y_{rs} , where $X_{rs}, Y_{rs} \in R(I)$, which means (X_{rs}, Y_{rs}) is double sequences of fuzzy real numbers.

Definition 1

A double sequence $(X, Y) = (X_{rs}, Y_{rs})$ of fuzzy real numbers is said to beconverge to the fuzzy numbers X_0, Y_0 , if for every $\epsilon > 0$, there exists $\gamma_0, S_0 \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $\bar{d}(X_{rs}, X_0) < \epsilon$ and $\bar{d}(Y_{rs}, Y_0) < \epsilon$ for all $\gamma \geq \gamma_0, S \geq S_0$, and consequently $\bar{d}((X_{rs}, X_0), (Y_{rs}, Y_0)) < \epsilon$, for all $\gamma \geq \gamma_0, S \geq S_0$.

Definition 2

A double sequence $(X, Y) = (X_{rs}, Y_{rs})$ of fuzzy real numbers is said to be a double Cauchy sequence, if for every $\epsilon > 0$ there exists $n_0 \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $\bar{d}(X_{ij}, X_{rs}) < \epsilon$ and $\bar{d}(Y_{ij}, Y_{rs}) < \epsilon$, for all $i \geq \gamma \geq n_0, j \geq S \geq n_0$, and consequently $\bar{d}((X_{ij}, X_{rs}), (Y_{ij}, Y_{rs})) < \epsilon$, for all $i \geq \gamma \geq n_0, j \geq S \geq n_0$.

Definition 3

A double sequence space $2E$ is said to be solid if $(F_{rs}, H_{rs}) \in 2E$, whenever $(X_{rs}, Y_{rs}) \in 2E$ and $|(F_{rs}, H_{rs})| \leq |(X_{rs}, Y_{rs})|$, for all $\gamma, s \in \mathbb{N}$.

Definition 4

A double sequence space $2E$ is said to be symmetric if $S(X_{rs}, Y_{rs}) \subset 2E$ whenever $(X_{rs}, Y_{rs}) \in 2E$, where $bS(X_{rs}, Y_{rs})$ denotes the set of all permutations of the elements of (X_{rs}, Y_{rs}) , that is $S(X_{rs}, Y_{rs}) = \{(X_{\pi(t), \pi(s)}, Y_{\pi(t), \pi(s)}) : \pi$ is a permutation of $\mathbb{N}\}$

Definition 5

A double sequence space $2E$ is said to be convergence-free if $(F_{rs}, H_{rs}) \in 2E$, whenever $(X_{rs}, Y_{rs}) \in 2E, (X_{rs}, Y_{rs}) = (\bar{0}, \bar{0})$ implies that $(F_{rs}, H_{rs}) = (\bar{0}, \bar{0})$.

Definition 6

A double sequence space $2E$ is said to be monotone. if $2E$ contains the cano- nical preimages of all its step spaces.

Lemma 1

A double sequence space $2E$ is solid implies that $2E$ is monotone. Let ϵ_c denoted the class of all subsets of \mathbb{N} these do not include more than c number of elements. $\phi = (\phi_{rs})$ is a non-decreasing sequence for all γ, s are positive real numbers such that $(\gamma + 1)(s + 1)\phi_{rs} \geq r\phi_{\gamma+1, s+1}$, for all $\gamma, s \in \mathbb{N}$.

Lindenstrauss and Tzafriri [16] used the idea of Orlicz function and introduced the sequence space L_m of single sequences, later Battor and Neamah [19] used that idea to construct a double sequence space: $L_M^2 = \{(X_{rs}, Y_{rs}) \in \omega^2 : \sum_{r=1}^\infty \sum_{s=1}^\infty [(M_1(\frac{|X_{rs}|}{\rho})) \vee (M_2(\frac{|Y_{rs}|}{\rho}))] < \infty$, for some $\rho > 0\}$,

Which is a Banach space under the norm:
 $\|(X_{rs}, Y_{rs})\|_M = \inf \{\rho > 0 : \sum_{r=1}^\infty \sum_{s=1}^\infty [(M_1(\frac{|X_{rs}|}{\rho})) \wedge (M_2(\frac{|Y_{rs}|}{\rho}))] \leq 1\}$,

Which is called a double Orlicz of a double sequence space where ω^2 is a family of all \mathbb{R}^2 or \mathbb{C}^2 double sequence, that is, (X_{rs}) and (Y_{rs}) are complex or real double sequence) and they conclusion that the double Orlicz of a double sequence space L_M^2 be closely related to the space L_p^2 , which is a double Orlicz double sequence space with $M(X, Y) = (M_1(X), M_2(Y)) = (X^p, Y^p)$, for $(1, 1) \leq (p, p) < (\infty, \infty)$ such that $M_1(X) = X^p$, for $1 \leq p < \infty$, and $M_2(Y) = Y^p$, for $1 \leq p < \infty$

Tripathy and Borgohain [[11]], Tripathy and Mahanta [[5]] introduced and studied many of the classes of Orlicz sequence spaces. In this paper, we introduce the difference double sequence space of fuzzy real numbers defined in a double Orlicz function as follows:

$$2m(M, \phi, \Delta_m^n, p)^F = \{(X, Y) = (X_{rs}, Y_{rs}) : \sup_{c \geq 1, \tau \in \epsilon_c} \sup_{d \geq 1, \tau' \in \epsilon_d} \frac{1}{\phi_c} \frac{1}{\phi_d} \sum_{\gamma \in \tau} \sum_{s \in \tau'} (M_1(\frac{\bar{d}(\Delta_m^n X_{rs}, \bar{0})}{\rho}) \vee M_2(\frac{\bar{d}(\Delta_m^n Y_{rs}, \bar{0})}{\rho}))^\rho < \infty, \text{ for some } \rho > 0\}, \text{ for } 0 < p < \infty.$$

Main Results

Theorem 1

(a) The double sequence space $2m(M, \phi, \Delta_m^n, p)^F$ is a complete metric space by the metric,

$$g_m((X, Y), (F, H)) = \sum_{k=1}^{mn} \bar{d}((X_{k\tau}, Y_{k\tau}), (F_{k\tau}, H_{k\tau})) + \inf \left\{ \rho > 0 : \sup_{c \geq 1, \tau \in \epsilon_c} \sup_{d \geq 1, \tau' \in \epsilon_d} \frac{1}{\phi_c} \frac{1}{\phi_d} \sum_{\gamma \in \tau} \sum_{s \in \tau'} \left(M_1 \left(\frac{\bar{d}(\Delta_m^n X_{rs}, \Delta_m^n Y_{rs})}{\rho} \right) \vee M_2 \left(\frac{\bar{d}(\Delta_m^n F_{rs}, \Delta_m^n H_{rs})}{\rho} \right) \right)^\rho < \infty \right\}$$

For $(X, Y), (F, H) \in 2m(M, \phi, \Delta_m^n, p)^F, m \geq 1, n \geq 1$ and for $1 \leq p < \infty$.

(b) The double sequence space $2m(M, \phi, \Delta_m^n, p)^F$ is a complete metric space by the metric,

$$g_m((X, Y), (F, H)) = \sum_{k=1}^{mn} \bar{d}((X_{k\tau}, Y_{k\tau}), (F_{k\tau}, H_{k\tau})) + \inf \left\{ \rho > 0 : \sup_{c \geq 1, \tau \in \epsilon_c} \sup_{d \geq 1, \tau' \in \epsilon_d} \frac{1}{\phi_c} \frac{1}{\phi_d} \left[\sum_{\gamma \in \tau} \sum_{s \in \tau'} (M_1(\frac{\bar{d}(\Delta_m^n X_{rs}, \Delta_m^n Y_{rs})}{\rho}) \vee M_2(\frac{\bar{d}(\Delta_m^n F_{rs}, \Delta_m^n H_{rs})}{\rho}))^\rho \right]^{\frac{1}{\rho}} \leq 1 \right\}$$

For $(X, Y), (F, H) \in 2m(M, \phi, \Delta_m^n, p)^F, m \geq 1, n \geq 1$ and for $1 \leq p < \infty$.

Proof(a)

Clearly, $2m(M, \phi, \Delta_m^n, p)^F$ is a metric space by the metric g , in above. We need to show that it is a complete metric space. Suppose that (X^i, Y^i) is a double Cauchy sequence in $2m(M, \phi, \Delta_m^n, p)^F$, Such that $(X^i), (Y^i)$ be a Cauchy sequence in $2m(M, \phi, \Delta_m^n, p)^F$, $2m(M, \phi, \Delta_m^n, p)^F$, respectively and $(X^i) = (X_{nq}^i)_{n,q=1}^\infty, (Y^i) = (Y_{nq}^i)_{n,q=1}^\infty$. Let $\epsilon > 0$ be given for a fixed $\eta > 0$, choose $t > 0$ such that $M_1\left(\frac{t\eta}{2}\right) \geq 1$ and $M_2\left(\frac{t\eta}{2}\right) \geq 1$, that is, $M\left(\frac{t\eta}{2}, \frac{t\eta}{2}\right) = \left(M_1\left(\frac{t\eta}{2}\right), M_2\left(\frac{t\eta}{2}\right)\right) \geq (1, 1)$. Then, there exists a positive integer $n_0(\epsilon)$ such that $gm_1(X^i, X^j) < \frac{\epsilon}{t\eta}$ and $gm_2(Y^i, Y^j) < \frac{\epsilon}{t\eta}, \forall i, j \geq n_0$, and consequently, $gm((X^i, X^j), (Y^i, Y^j)) < \frac{\epsilon}{t\eta}, \forall i, j \geq n_0$. By definition of g ,

We get

$$\sum_{k=1}^{mn} \sum_{l=1}^{mn} \bar{d}((X_{kl}^i, X_{kl}^j), (Y_{kl}^i, Y_{kl}^j)) + \inf \left\{ \rho > 0 : \sup_{c \geq 1, \tau \in \epsilon_c} \sup_{d \geq 1, \tau' \in \epsilon_d} \frac{1}{\phi_c} \frac{1}{\phi_d} \sum_{\gamma \in \tau} \sum_{S \in \tau'} \left(M_1 \left(\frac{\bar{d}(\Delta_m^n X_{rs}^i, \Delta_m^n X_{rs}^j)}{\rho} \right) \vee M_2 \left(\frac{\bar{d}(\Delta_m^n Y_{rs}^i, \Delta_m^n Y_{rs}^j)}{\rho} \right) \right)^\rho \leq 1 \right\} < \epsilon, \forall i, j \geq n_0, \dots (3, 1)$$

This implies, $\sum_{k=1}^{mn} \sum_{l=1}^{mn} \bar{d}((X_{kl}^i, X_{kl}^j), (Y_{kl}^i, Y_{kl}^j)) < \epsilon, \forall i, j \geq n_0$.

And then we have $\bar{d}((X_{k\iota}^i, X_{k\iota}^j), (Y_{k\iota}^i, Y_{k\iota}^j)) < \epsilon, \forall i, j \geq n_0$,

$k, \iota = 1, 2, 3, \dots, mn$.

Thus $(X_{k\iota}^i, Y_{k\iota}^i)$, for $k, \iota = 1, 2, 3, \dots, mn$ is a double Cauchy sequence in $R_2(I)$, and hence it is convergent in $R_2(I)$, by the completeness property of $R_2(I)$.

Let, $\lim_{i \rightarrow \infty} (X_{k\iota}^i) = X_{k\iota}, \lim_{i \rightarrow \infty} (Y_{k\iota}^i) = (Y_{k\iota})$, for $k, \iota = 1, 2, 3, \dots, mn$.

So, $\lim_{i \rightarrow \infty} (X_{k\iota}^i, Y_{k\iota}^i) = (X_{k\iota}, Y_{k\iota})$ for $k, \iota = 1, 2, 3, \dots, mn \dots (3, 2)$

Furthermore

$$\sup_{c \geq 1, \tau \in \epsilon_c} \sup_{d \geq 1, \tau' \in \epsilon_d} \frac{1}{\phi_c} \frac{1}{\phi_d} \sum_{\gamma \in \tau} \sum_{S \in \tau'} \left(M_1 \left(\frac{\bar{d}(\Delta_m^n X_{rs}^i, \Delta_m^n X_{rs}^j)}{\rho} \right) \vee M_2 \left(\frac{\bar{d}(\Delta_m^n Y_{rs}^i, \Delta_m^n Y_{rs}^j)}{\rho} \right) \right)^\rho \leq 1, \forall i, j \geq n_0 \dots (3, 3)$$

For $c=1, d=1$ and τ, τ' varying over ϵ_c, ϵ_d , we get,

$$\sum_{\gamma \in \tau} \sum_{S \in \tau'} \left(M_1 \left(\frac{\bar{d}(\Delta_m^n X_{rs}^i, \Delta_m^n X_{rs}^j)}{gm_1(X^i, X^j)} \right) \vee M_2 \left(\frac{\bar{d}(\Delta_m^n Y_{rs}^i, \Delta_m^n Y_{rs}^j)}{gm_2(Y^i, Y^j)} \right) \right)^\rho \leq \phi_1 \phi_1, \forall j \geq n_0$$

$$\Rightarrow \left[M_1 \left(\frac{\bar{d}(\Delta_m^n X_{rs}^i, \Delta_m^n X_{rs}^j)}{gm_1(X^i, X^j)} \right), M_2 \left(\frac{\bar{d}(\Delta_m^n Y_{rs}^i, \Delta_m^n Y_{rs}^j)}{gm_2(Y^i, Y^j)} \right) \right] \leq \phi_1^{\frac{1}{\rho}} \phi_1^{\frac{1}{\rho}} \leq (M_1\left(\frac{t\eta}{2}\right), M_2\left(\frac{t\eta}{2}\right)), \forall i, j \geq n_0$$

Using the continuity of M so M_1, M_2 , we have

$$\bar{d}(\Delta_m^n X_{rs}^i, \Delta_m^n X_{rs}^j) \leq \frac{t\eta}{2} \cdot gm_1(X^i, X^j) \text{ and } \bar{d}(\Delta_m^n Y_{rs}^i, \Delta_m^n Y_{rs}^j) \leq \frac{t\eta}{2} \cdot gm_2(Y^i, Y^j), \forall i, j \geq n_0,$$

$$\Rightarrow \bar{d}(\Delta_m^n X_{rs}^i, \Delta_m^n X_{rs}^j) < \frac{t\eta}{2} \cdot \frac{\epsilon}{t\eta} = \frac{\epsilon}{2}, \bar{d}(\Delta_m^n Y_{rs}^i, \Delta_m^n Y_{rs}^j) < \frac{t\eta}{2} \cdot \frac{\epsilon}{t\eta} = \frac{\epsilon}{2}, \forall i, j \geq n_0,$$

$$\text{Then, we get } \bar{d}((\Delta_m^n X_{rs}^i, \Delta_m^n X_{rs}^j), (\Delta_m^n Y_{rs}^i, \Delta_m^n Y_{rs}^j)) \leq \frac{t\eta}{2} \cdot gm((X^i, X^j), (Y^i, Y^j)), \forall i, j \geq n_0,$$

$$\Rightarrow \bar{d}((\Delta_m^n X_{rs}^i, \Delta_m^n X_{rs}^j), (\Delta_m^n Y_{rs}^i, \Delta_m^n Y_{rs}^j)) < \frac{t\eta}{2} \cdot \frac{\epsilon}{t\eta} = \frac{\epsilon}{2}, \forall i, j \geq n_0.$$

Which implies $(\Delta_m^n X_{rs}^i, \Delta_m^n Y_{rs}^j)$ is a double Cauchy sequence in $R^2(I)$ and so is convergent in $R^2(I)$ by the completeness property of $R^2(I)$

Next, we have to prove that, $\lim_i (X^i, Y^i) = (X, Y)$ and $(X, Y) \in 2m(M, \phi, \Delta_m^n, p)^F$

Let, $\lim_i (\Delta_m^n X_{rs}^i) = (F_{rs}) \in R(I)$, and $\lim_i (\Delta_m^n Y_{rs}^i) = (H_{rs}) \in R(I)$, for each $\gamma, S \in N$. That is, $\lim_i (\Delta_m^n X_{rs}^i, \Delta_m^n Y_{rs}^i) = (F_{rs}, H_{rs}) \in R^2(I)$, for each $\gamma, S \in N$.

For $\gamma, S = 1$, we have, from (1.1) and (3.2) that

$$\lim_{i \rightarrow \infty} (X_{mn+1, mn+1}^i, Y_{mn+1, mn+1}^i) = (X_{mn+1, mn+1}, Y_{mn+1, mn+1}), \text{ for } m \geq 1, n \geq 1.$$

Proceeding in this way inductively, we have $\lim_{i \rightarrow \infty} (X_{rs}^i, Y_{rs}^i) = (X_{rs}, Y_{rs})$ for each $\gamma, S \in N$.

Also, $\lim_i (\Delta_m^n X_{rs}^i, \Delta_m^n Y_{rs}^i) = (\Delta_m^n X_{rs}, \Delta_m^n Y_{rs})$, for each $\gamma, S \in N$.

Now, by using the continuity of M so M_1, M_2 we get the following

from (3.3):

$$\sup_{c \geq 1, \tau \in \epsilon_c} \sup_{d \geq 1, \tau' \in \epsilon_d} \frac{1}{\phi_c} \frac{1}{\phi_d} \sum_{\gamma \in \tau} \sum_{S \in \tau'} \left(M_1 \left(\frac{\bar{d}(\Delta_m^n X_{rs}^i, \Delta_m^n X_{rs}^j)}{\rho} \right) \vee M_2 \left(\frac{\bar{d}(\Delta_m^n Y_{rs}^i, \Delta_m^n Y_{rs}^j)}{\rho} \right) \right)^\rho \leq 1,$$

for some $\rho > 0$, And $i \geq n_0$. Now, if we consider the infimum of such ρ s and using (3.1),

We find

$$\inf \left\{ \rho > 0 : \sup_{c \geq 1, \tau \in \epsilon_c} \sup_{d \geq 1, \tau' \in \epsilon_d} \frac{1}{\phi_c} \frac{1}{\phi_d} \sum_{\gamma \in \tau} \sum_{S \in \tau'} \left(M_1 \left(\frac{\bar{d}(\Delta_m^n X_{rs}^i, \Delta_m^n X_{rs}^j)}{\rho} \right) \vee M_2 \left(\frac{\bar{d}(\Delta_m^n Y_{rs}^i, \Delta_m^n Y_{rs}^j)}{\rho} \right) \right)^\rho \leq 1 \right\} < \epsilon, \forall i \geq n_0,$$

Thus,

$$\sum_{k=1}^{mn} \sum_{l=1}^{mn} \bar{d}((X_{kl}^i, X_{kl}^j), (Y_{kl}^i, Y_{kl}^j)) + \inf \left\{ \rho > 0 : \sup_{c \geq 1, \tau \in \epsilon_c} \sup_{d \geq 1, \tau' \in \epsilon_d} \frac{1}{\phi_c} \frac{1}{\phi_d} \sum_{\gamma \in \tau} \sum_{S \in \tau'} \left(M_1 \left(\frac{\bar{d}(\Delta_m^n X_{rs}^i, \Delta_m^n X_{rs}^j)}{\rho} \right) \vee M_2 \left(\frac{\bar{d}(\Delta_m^n Y_{rs}^i, \Delta_m^n Y_{rs}^j)}{\rho} \right) \right)^\rho \leq 1 \right\} < \epsilon + \epsilon = 2\epsilon, \forall i \geq n_0.$$

Which implies that, $g((X^i, X), (Y^i, Y)) < 2\epsilon, \forall i \geq n_0$. That is, $\lim_i (X^i, Y^i) = (X, Y)$.

Now, we shall show that $(X, Y) \in 2m(M, \phi, \Delta_m^n, p)^F$, we have well known that, $g((X, \bar{0}), (Y, \bar{0})) \leq g((X^n, X), (Y^n, Y)) + g((X^n, \bar{0}), (Y^n, \bar{0})) < \epsilon + M, \forall n \geq n_0$, Which means $g((X, \bar{0}), (Y, \bar{0}))$ is finite, implies that $(X, Y) \in 2m(M, \phi, \Delta_m^n, p)^F$.

Hence $2m(M, \phi, \Delta_m^n, p)^F$ is a complete metric space.

Theorem 2

(b) This part can be proved by following similar techniques.

The double sequence space $2m(M, \phi, \Delta_m^n, p)^F$ is not solid, for $0 < p < \infty$

Proof

Consider the following example to prove the result.

Example 1

Let $m=3, n=2, p=2$. and $M(X, Y) = (M_1(X), M_2(Y)) = (|X|, |Y|)$, for all $(X, Y) \in (0, \infty) \times (0, \infty)$.

Let the double sequence $(X_{rs}, Y_{rs}) = (\bar{\gamma}, \bar{\gamma})$ for $\gamma, S \in N$ and $\phi_c = c, \phi_d = d$ for all $c, d \in N$. Then, $\bar{d}((\Delta_3^2 X_{rs}, \bar{0}), (\Delta_3^2 Y_{rs}, \bar{0})) = (0, 0)$, for $\gamma, S \in N$.

Hence, we have,

$$\sup_{c \geq 1, \tau \in \epsilon_c} \sup_{d \geq 1, \tau' \in \epsilon_d} \frac{1}{\phi_c} \frac{1}{\phi_d} \sum_{\gamma \in \tau} \sum_{S \in \tau'} \left(M_1 \left(\frac{\bar{d}(\Delta_3^2 X_{rs}, \bar{0})}{\rho} \right) \vee M_2 \left(\frac{\bar{d}(\Delta_3^2 Y_{rs}, \bar{0})}{\rho} \right) \right)^\rho < \infty, \text{ for some } \rho > 0, \text{ this implies,}$$

$(X_{rs}) \in 2m(M_1, \phi, \Delta_m^n, 2)^F$ and $(Y_{rs}) \in 2m(M_2, \phi, \Delta_m^n, 2)^F$, and consequently, $(X_{rs}, Y_{rs}) \in 2m(M, \phi, \Delta_m^n, 2)^F$, where $b=cd$.

Let $(\alpha_{rs}, \beta_{rs})$ be a double sequence of scalars defined as,

$$(\alpha_{rs}, \beta_{rs}) = \begin{cases} (1, 1), & \text{for } \gamma \text{ is even,} \\ (0, 0), & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \Rightarrow (\alpha_{rs} X_{rs}, \beta_{rs}, Y_{rs}) =$$

$$\begin{cases} (\bar{\gamma}, \bar{\gamma}), & \text{for } \gamma \text{ is even,} \\ (\bar{0}, \bar{0}), & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

$$\Rightarrow \sup_{c \geq 1, \tau \in \epsilon_c} \sup_{d \geq 1, \tau' \in \epsilon_d} \frac{1}{\phi_c} \frac{1}{\phi_d} \sum_{\gamma \in \tau} \sum_{S \in \tau'} \left(M_1 \left(\frac{\bar{d}(\Delta_3^2 \alpha_{rs} X_{rs}, \bar{0})}{\rho} \right) \vee M_2 \left(\frac{\bar{d}(\Delta_3^2 \beta_{rs} Y_{rs}, \bar{0})}{\rho} \right) \right)^\rho = \infty, \text{ for any fixed } \rho > 0, \text{ which shows that,}$$

$(\alpha_{rs} X_{rs}) \in 2m(M_1, c, \Delta_3^2, 2)^F, (\beta_{rs} Y_{rs}) \in 2m(M_2, d, \Delta_3^2, 2)^F$.

So, $(\alpha_{rs} X_{rs}, \beta_{rs} Y_{rs}) \in 2m(M, b, \Delta_3^2, 2)^F$, where $b=cd$.

Hence, $2m(M, \phi, \Delta_m^n, 2)^F$ is not solid for $0 < p < \infty$.

Theorem 3

The double sequence space $2m(M, \phi, \Delta_m^n, p)^F$ is not symmetric, for $0 < p < \infty$.

Proof

The result follows from the following example:

Example 2

Let $m=1, n=1, p=\frac{1}{2}$ and $M(X, Y) = (M_1(X), M_2(Y)) = (X^2, Y^2), \forall (X, Y) \in (0, \infty) \times (0, \infty)$.
 Let the double sequence $(X_{rs}, Y_{rs}) = (\gamma, \gamma)$, for $\gamma, s \in \mathbb{N}$ and $\phi_c = c, \phi_d = d$, for all $c, d \in \mathbb{N}$.
 Then, $\bar{d}((\Delta X_{rs}, \bar{0}), (\Delta Y_{rs}, \bar{0})) = (1, 1)$, for all $\gamma, s \in \mathbb{N}$, which shows that $(X_{rs}, Y_{rs}) \in 2m(b, \Delta, \frac{1}{2})^F$ where $b=cd$.
 Now, let (F_{rs}, H_{rs}) be a rearrangement of (X_{rs}, Y_{rs}) such that, $(F_{rs}, H_{rs}) = ((X_{11}, Y_{11}), (X_{22}, Y_{22}), (X_{44}, Y_{44}), (X_{33}, Y_{33}), (X_{99}, Y_{99}), (X_{55}, Y_{55}), (X_{16}, Y_{16}), \dots)$
 Then, we get $\bar{d}((\Delta F_{rs}, \bar{0}), (\Delta H_{rs}, \bar{0})) \approx (\gamma - (\gamma - 1)^2, \gamma - (\gamma - 1)^2) \approx (\gamma^2, \gamma^2)$, for all $\gamma^2, \gamma, s \in \mathbb{N}$, which implies, $\sup_{c \geq 1, \tau \in \epsilon_c} \sup_{d \geq 1, \tau' \in \epsilon_d} \frac{1}{c} \frac{1}{d} \sum_{\gamma \in \tau} \sum_{s \in \tau'} (M_1(\frac{\bar{d}(\Delta F_{rs}, \bar{0})}{\rho})) \vee (M_2(\frac{\bar{d}(\Delta H_{rs}, \bar{0})}{\rho}))^{\frac{1}{p}} = \infty$, for some $\rho > 0$.
 Hence, $(F_{rs}) \in 2m(M_1, c, \Delta, \frac{1}{2})^F$ and $(H_{rs}) \in 2m(M_2, d, \Delta, \frac{1}{2})^F$.
 And consequently, $(F_{rs}, H_{rs}) \in 2m(M, b, \Delta, \frac{1}{2})^F$, where $b=cd$.
 Thus, the double sequence space $2m(M, \phi, \Delta_m^n, p)^F$ is not symmetric for $0 < p < \infty$.

Proposition 1

The double sequence space $2m(M, \phi, \Delta_m^n, p)^F$ is not convergence-free.

Proof

To prove that we take the following example.
 Let $m=4$ and $n=1, p=\frac{1}{2}$. Let $M(X, Y) = (X^4, Y^4)$, for all $(X, Y) \in (0, \infty) \times (0, \infty)$
 And $\phi_c = c, \phi_d = d$ for all $c, d \in \mathbb{N}$.

Consider the double sequence (X_{rs}, Y_{rs}) defined as

$$(X_{rs}, Y_{rs})(t) = \begin{cases} (1 + rt, 1 + rt), & \text{for } t \in [-1/r, 0], \\ (1 - rt, 1 - rt), & \text{for } t \in [0, 1/r], \\ (0, 0), & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

Then $(\Delta_4 X_{rs}, \Delta_4 Y_{rs})(t) = \begin{cases} (1 + \frac{r(t+4)}{2r+4}, t, 1 + \frac{r(t+4)}{2r+4}), & \text{for } t \in [-\frac{2r+4}{r(t+4)}, 0], \\ (1 - \frac{r(t+4)}{2r+4}, t, 1 - \frac{r(t+4)}{2r+4}), & \text{for } t \in [0, \frac{2r+4}{r(t+4)}], \\ (0, 0), & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$

$\Rightarrow \bar{d}((\Delta_4 X_{rs}, \bar{0}), (\Delta_4 Y_{rs}, \bar{0})) = (\frac{2r+4}{r(t+4)}, \frac{2r+4}{r(t+4)}) = (\frac{2}{r+1} + \frac{4}{r(t+4)}, \frac{2}{r+1} + \frac{4}{r(t+4)})$

Then it follows that,
 $\sup_{c \geq 1, \tau \in \epsilon_c} \sup_{d \geq 1, \tau' \in \epsilon_d} \frac{1}{c} \frac{1}{d} \sum_{\tau \in \tau} \sum_{s \in \tau'} (M_1(\frac{\bar{d}(\Delta_4 X_{rs}, \bar{0})}{\rho})) \vee (M_2(\frac{\bar{d}(\Delta_4 Y_{rs}, \bar{0})}{\rho}))^{\frac{1}{p}} < \infty$ for all $\rho > 0$.
 Which implies $(X_{rs}) \in 2m(M_1, c, \Delta_4, \frac{1}{2})^F$ and $(Y_{rs}) \in 2m(M_2, d, \Delta_4, \frac{1}{2})^F$
 so, $(X_{rs}, Y_{rs}) \in 2m(M, b, \Delta_4, \frac{1}{2})^F$, where $b=cd$.

Now, let (F_{rs}, H_{rs}) be another double sequence defined as,

$$(F_{rs}, H_{rs})(t) = \begin{cases} (1 + t/r^2, 1 + t/r^2), & \text{for } t \in [-r^2, 0], \\ (1 - t/r^2, 1 - t/r^2), & \text{for } t \in [0, r^2]. \end{cases}$$

Furthermore, $(\Delta_4 F_{rs}, \Delta_4 H_{rs})(t) = \begin{cases} (1 + \frac{t}{2r^2+8r+16}, 1 + \frac{t}{2r^2+8r+16}), & \text{for } t \in [-(2r^2 + 8r + 16), 0] \\ (1 - \frac{t}{2r^2+8r+16}, 1 - \frac{t}{2r^2+8r+16}), & \text{for } t \in [0, -(2r^2 + 8r + 16)] \\ (0, 0), & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$

But, $\bar{d}((\Delta_4 F_{rs}, \bar{0}), (\Delta_4 H_{rs}, \bar{0})) = (2r^2 + 8r + 16, 2r^2 + 8r + 16)$, for $r, s \in \mathbb{N}$,
 Which implies,
 $\sup_{c \geq 1, \tau \in \epsilon_c} \sup_{d \geq 1, \tau' \in \epsilon_d} \frac{1}{c} \frac{1}{d} \sum_{\gamma \in \tau} \sum_{s \in \tau'} (M_1(\frac{\bar{d}(\Delta_4 F_{rs}, \bar{0})}{\rho})) \vee (M_2(\frac{\bar{d}(\Delta_4 H_{rs}, \bar{0})}{\rho}))^{\frac{1}{p}} = \infty$, for some $\rho > 0$, which means that,
 $(F_{rs}) \in 2m(M_1, c, \Delta_4, \frac{1}{2})^F$. $(H_{rs}) \in 2m(M_2, d, \Delta_4, \frac{1}{2})^F$,
 That is, $(F_{rs}, H_{rs}) \in 2m(M, b, \Delta_4, \frac{1}{2})^F$, where $b=cd$.
 Hence $2m(M, \phi, \Delta_m^n, p)^F$ is not convergence-free.

Proposition 2

$2m(M, \phi, \Delta_m^n, p)^F \subseteq 2m(M, \phi, \Delta_m^n, p)^F$ for all $1 \leq p \leq \infty$

Proof

Let $(X, Y) \in 2m(M, \phi, \Delta_m^n)^F$, then we have,
 $\sup_{c \geq 1, \tau \in \epsilon_c} \sup_{d \geq 1, \tau' \in \epsilon_d} \frac{1}{\phi_c} \frac{1}{\phi_d} \sum_{\gamma \in \tau} \sum_{s \in \tau'} (M_1(\frac{\bar{d}(\Delta_m^n X_{rs}, \bar{0})}{\rho})) \vee (M_2(\frac{\bar{d}(\Delta_m^n Y_{rs}, \bar{0})}{\rho})) = L < \infty$,
 For any fixed $\rho > 0$.
 Hence, for each fixed c, d and $\epsilon \in \epsilon_c, \tau' \in \epsilon_d$, respectively, we get, for $\rho > 0$ that $\sum_{\gamma \in \tau} \sum_{s \in \tau'} (M_1(\frac{\bar{d}(\Delta_m^n X_{rs}, \bar{0})}{\rho})) \vee (M_2(\frac{\bar{d}(\Delta_m^n Y_{rs}, \bar{0})}{\rho})) \leq L \phi_c \phi_d$.
Then,
 $[\sum_{\gamma \in \tau} \sum_{s \in \tau'} (M_1(\frac{\bar{d}(\Delta_m^n X_{rs}, \bar{0})}{\rho})) \vee (M_2(\frac{\bar{d}(\Delta_m^n Y_{rs}, \bar{0})}{\rho}))]^{\frac{1}{p}} \leq L \phi_c \phi_d$,
 $\sup_{c \geq 1, \tau \in \epsilon_c} \sup_{d \geq 1, \tau' \in \epsilon_d} \frac{1}{\phi_c} \frac{1}{\phi_d} [\sum_{\gamma \in \tau} \sum_{s \in \tau'} (M_1(\frac{\bar{d}(\Delta_m^n X_{rs}, \bar{0})}{\rho})) \vee (M_2(\frac{\bar{d}(\Delta_m^n Y_{rs}, \bar{0})}{\rho}))]^{\frac{1}{p}} \leq L < \infty$,
 Which implies that, $(X, Y) \in 2m(M, \phi, \Delta_m^n, p)^F$, for $1 \leq p < \infty$

Proposition 3

$2m(M, \phi, \Delta_m^n, p)^F \subseteq 2m(M, \psi, \Delta_m^n, p)^F$, If and only if $\sup_{c \geq 1} \sup_{d \geq 1} \frac{\phi_c \phi_d}{\psi_c \psi_d} < \infty$, for $0 < p < \infty$.

Proof

Suppose that, $\sup_{c \geq 1} \sup_{d \geq 1} \frac{\phi_c \phi_d}{\psi_c \psi_d} < \infty$, then we get,
 $\phi_c \phi_d \leq L \psi_c \psi_d$. If $(X_{rs}, Y_{rs}) \in 2m(M, \phi, \Delta_m^n, p)^F$, then
 $\sup_{c \geq 1, \tau \in \epsilon_c} \sup_{d \geq 1, \tau' \in \epsilon_d} \frac{1}{\phi_c} \frac{1}{\phi_d} \sum_{\gamma \in \tau} \sum_{s \in \tau'} (M_1(\frac{\bar{d}(\Delta_m^n X_{rs}, \bar{0})}{\rho})) \vee (M_2(\frac{\bar{d}(\Delta_m^n Y_{rs}, \bar{0})}{\rho}))^p < \infty$,
 $\Rightarrow \sup_{c \geq 1, \tau \in \epsilon_c} \sup_{d \geq 1, \tau' \in \epsilon_d} \frac{1}{L \psi_c} \frac{1}{L \psi_d} \sum_{\gamma \in \tau} \sum_{s \in \tau'} (M_1(\frac{\bar{d}(\Delta_m^n X_{rs}, \bar{0})}{\rho})) \vee (M_2(\frac{\bar{d}(\Delta_m^n Y_{rs}, \bar{0})}{\rho}))^p < \infty$,
 That shows, $(X_{rs}, Y_{rs}) \in 2m(M, \psi, \Delta_m^n, p)^F$, it means $2m(M, \phi, \Delta_m^n, p)^F \subseteq 2m(M, \psi, \Delta_m^n, p)^F$.
 Conversely, suppose that, $2m(M, \phi, \Delta_m^n, p)^F \subseteq 2m(M, \psi, \Delta_m^n, p)^F$.
 To prove that $\sup_{c \geq 1} \sup_{d \geq 1} \frac{\phi_c \phi_d}{\psi_c \psi_d} = \sup_{c \geq 1} \sup_{d \geq 1} (\eta_c \delta_d) < \infty$
 Suppose that $\sup_{c \geq 1} \sup_{d \geq 1} (\eta_c \delta_d) = \infty$. Then there exists subsequences $(\eta_{c_i}), (\delta_{d_i})$, respectively such that, $\lim_{i \rightarrow \infty} (\eta_{c_i}) = \infty$ and $\lim_{i \rightarrow \infty} (\delta_{d_i}) = \infty$. Then, for $(X_{rs}, Y_{rs}) \in 2m(M, \phi, \Delta_m^n, p)^F$,
We have,
 $\sup_{c \geq 1, \tau \in \epsilon_c} \sup_{d \geq 1, \tau' \in \epsilon_d} \frac{1}{\psi_c} \frac{1}{\psi_d} \sum_{\gamma \in \tau} \sum_{s \in \tau'} (M_1(\frac{\bar{d}(\Delta_m^n X_{rs}, \bar{0})}{\rho})) \vee (M_2(\frac{\bar{d}(\Delta_m^n Y_{rs}, \bar{0})}{\rho}))^p$
 $\geq \sup_{c \geq 1, \tau \in \epsilon_c} \sup_{d \geq 1, \tau' \in \epsilon_d} \frac{\eta_{c_i} \delta_{d_i}}{\phi_{c_i} \phi_{d_i}} \sum_{\gamma \in \tau} \sum_{s \in \tau'} (M_1(\frac{\bar{d}(\Delta_m^n X_{rs}, \bar{0})}{\rho})) \vee (M_2(\frac{\bar{d}(\Delta_m^n Y_{rs}, \bar{0})}{\rho}))^p = \infty$,
 $\Rightarrow \sup_{c \geq 1, \tau \in \epsilon_c} \sup_{d \geq 1, \tau' \in \epsilon_d} \frac{1}{\psi_c} \frac{1}{\psi_d} \sum_{\gamma \in \tau} \sum_{s \in \tau'} (M_1(\frac{\bar{d}(\Delta_m^n X_{rs}, \bar{0})}{\rho})) \vee (M_2(\frac{\bar{d}(\Delta_m^n Y_{rs}, \bar{0})}{\rho}))^p = \infty$, which implies that $(X_{rs}, Y_{rs}) \notin 2m(M, \psi, \Delta_m^n, p)^F$, a contradiction. This completes the proof.

Corollary 1

$2m(M, \phi, \Delta_m^n, p)^F = 2m(M, \psi, \Delta_m^n, p)^F$,
 If and only if $\sup_{c \geq 1} \sup_{d \geq 1} (\eta_c \delta_d) = \infty$ and $\sup_{c \geq 1} \sup_{d \geq 1} (\eta_c^{-1} \delta_d^{-1}) < \infty$, Where $\eta_c = \phi_c / \psi_c, \delta_d = \phi_d / \psi_d$, for $0 < p < \infty$.

Theorem 4

$L_p^2(M, \Delta_m^n)^F \subseteq 2m(M, \phi, \Delta_m^n, p)^F \subseteq {}^2_\infty(M, \Delta_m^n)^F$ for all $1 \leq p < \infty$.

Proof

By taking $M(X, Y) = (M_1(X), M_2(Y)) = (X^p, Y^p)$, for $(1, 1) \leq (p, p) < (\infty, \infty)$ such that $M_1(X) = X^p$, for $1 \leq p < \infty$, and $M_2(Y) = Y^p$, for $1 \leq p < \infty$, and $\phi_n = 1, \delta_n = 1$, for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$, then we get that $2m(M, \phi, \Delta_m^n, p)^F = L_p^2(M, \Delta_m^n)^F$. this completes the first inclusion.
 Next, suppose that, $(X_{rs}, Y_{rs}) \in 2m(M, \phi, \Delta_m^n, p)^F$ which implies that

$\sup_{c \geq 1, \tau \in \varepsilon_c} \sup_{d \geq 1, \tau' \in \varepsilon_d} \frac{1}{\phi_c} \frac{1}{\phi_d} [\sum_{\gamma \in \tau} \sum_{S \in \tau'} (M_1(\frac{\bar{d}(\Delta_m^n X_{rs}, \bar{0})}{\rho})) \vee M_2(\frac{\bar{d}(\Delta_m^n Y_{rs}, \bar{0})}{\rho}))]^{\frac{1}{p}} = L < \infty$. For $c=1, d=1$, we get $[M_1(\frac{\bar{d}(\Delta_m^n X_{rs}, \bar{0})}{\rho}) \vee M_2(\frac{\bar{d}(\Delta_m^n Y_{rs}, \bar{0})}{\rho})] \leq L(\phi_1, \phi_1), r \in \tau, S \in \tau'$.
 $\Rightarrow \sup_{r \geq 1} \sup_{s \geq 1} [M_1(\frac{\bar{d}(\Delta_m^n X_{rs}, \bar{0})}{\rho}) \vee M_2(\frac{\bar{d}(\Delta_m^n Y_{rs}, \bar{0})}{\rho})] < \infty$ Thus
 $\Rightarrow \sup_{r \geq 1} \sup_{s \geq 1} [M_1(\frac{\bar{d}(\Delta_m^n X_{rs}, \bar{0})}{\rho}) \vee M_2(\frac{\bar{d}(\Delta_m^n Y_{rs}, \bar{0})}{\rho})] < \infty (X_{rs}, Y_{rs}) \in \iota_{\infty}^2(M, \Delta_m^n)^F$.
 Then we obtain the proof.

Proposition 5

$2m(M, \phi, \Delta_m^n, p)^F = L_p^2(M, \Delta_m^n)^F$. If and only if, $\sup_{c \geq 1} \sup_{d \geq 1} (\phi_c \phi_d) < \infty$, and $\sup_{c \geq 1} \sup_{d \geq 1} (\phi_c^{-1} \phi_d^{-1}) < \infty$.

Proof

Putting $\psi_n = 1$, for all $n \in N$ in corollary 1, then we get the result easily.

Corollary 2

$2m(M, \phi, \Delta_m^n, p)^F = L_p^2(M, \Delta_m^n)^F$ if $\lim_{c \rightarrow \infty} (\frac{\phi_c}{c}) > 0$ and $\lim_{d \rightarrow \infty} (\frac{\phi_d}{d}) > 0$ for $0 < p < \infty$.

Proof

Its trifle

Conclusions

We have improved numerous inclusion results also we introduce the difference double sequence space of fuzzy real numbers defined in a double Orlicz function, that the double sequence space is not convergence-free. The double sequence space is not symmetric, for

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